

[Wizzacom](#) gives away dream prizes for a small fee as \$0.05 per ticket. As portion of the donations is donated to a cause.

One of the prizes given by Wizzacom is McLaren 720S. The McLaren 720S is a supercar, manufactured by McLaren since 2018. It inaugurates the second generation of the McLaren Automotive Super Series range, making effective the generational replacement of the McLaren MP4-12C, which later became known as McLaren 12C -shortly- and that it was later updated to be known as the McLaren 650S. The McLaren 720S is a completely new sports car, with a new platform and significant aerodynamic and technological improvements over its predecessors. It is the sportiest range from McLaren Automotive, with the permission of a McLaren P1 that was produced in limited series and a new, even more powerful and exclusive supercar, which has been announced as the successor to the McLaren F1.

From Wizzacom share that, among the mid-engined two-seater sports cars that aspire to rival the McLaren 720S coupe we find the Lamborghini Huracán and the Ferrari F8 Tributo. And a product that most likely can be measured from you to you, and even beat in certain aspects, its rivals Ferrari and Lamborghini.

McLaren 720S exterior design:

As for the most outstanding characteristics of the McLaren 720S (which is given away for a small fee as \$0.05 per ticket), we cannot forget its aerodynamics. McLaren has worked hard to achieve a sports car with excellent aerodynamic performance and also to cool its central engine - located immediately behind the cabin. Thus, the McLaren 720S dispenses with air inlets in the rear wings, but it has managed to cool the engine with air inlets that are based on channels through which the air flows to the rear.

The McLaren 720S which is one of the [Wizza sweepstakes](#), is also the premiere of a new, more elaborate aesthetic philosophy, but at the same time minimalist that would also mark the development of other models that would later reach the Working catalog. See video of the McLaren 720S.

McLaren 720S interior design:

On board, it's the most technological McLaren we've seen yet, with advanced mobile instrumentation that pivots to suit the needs of road and track driving, so the McLaren 720S always displays only the information it needs. From Wizzacom share that the aesthetic is very sporty, omitting superfluous elements and using materials such as Alcantara and leather in an interior in which everything is focused on enjoying driving.

The McLaren 720S debuts the new generation of the Proactive Chassis Control system that seeks the highest traction capacity in any environment. It also features the house's second generation carbon fiber monocoque chassis, the McLaren Monocage II.

Wizzacom gives an equal chance to anyone [to win something epic](#).